

COMPOSITE PHASE CHANGE MATERIALS WITH ENHANCED THERMAL DIFFUSIVITY

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1 Introduction

Phase Change Materials (PCM) are substances with high latent heat at a given temperature. The heat is absorbed or released during the phase change from solid to liquid and vice-versa, and therefore such material may be called as the latent heat stores. [1]

The thermal conductivity of conventional PCM can be increased by the use of materials with high conductivity. The use of materials with high thermal conductivity in order to improve the performance PCM materials is carried out in several ways [2]:

- solutioning phase change material of the porous material with high thermal conductivity,
- a dispersion of particles of a high conductivity in the PCM,
- the introduction of metal structures in the PCM.

Although conventional PCMs have high energy density, there is low rate of melting and solidification [1], because all conventional PCM, both organic and inorganic materials have very low thermal conductivity in the range of 0.1 to 0.6 W / m K. During melting, the heat is transferred from the PCM first by conduction and then by convection. This is because the melting front moves into the material farther away from the heat source and the heat source is formed between the solid material and the buffer of the liquid fraction which has a much lower thermal conductivity and energy transfer by conduction of heat through the material becomes negligible compared to conduction by convection (the result of the density difference in the liquid fraction PCM). [3]

Paraffin wax consists of a mixture of mostly straight chain alkanes CH₃–(CH₂)–CH₃. The crystallization

of the (CH₃)-chain release a large amount of latent heat. Both the melting point and latent heat of fusion increase with chain length. Paraffin qualifies as heat of fusion storage materials due to their availability in a large temperature range. Paraffin show little volume changes on melting and have low vapor pressure in the melt form. For these properties of the paraffins, system-using paraffins usually have very long freeze–melt cycle. The melting point of alkane increases with the increasing number of carbon atoms. They show some undesirable properties such as: (i) low thermal conductivity, (ii) noncompatible with the plastic container and (iii) moderately flammable. [3].

In recent 12 years, a highly evolved carbon nanostructures in the form of fullerenes, carbon nanotubes, and graphene, and also increases the use of diamond powder in the study. These materials are becoming more widely available in the market as products. All are characterized by a very high thermal conductivity (more than 1000 W / mK in different directions). [4-20]

2 Motivation

The greater heat fluxes on small areas occur in technological problems and applications. There are a lot of active and passive methods for solving the heat sink in such structures. One of the passive methods is using phase change materials. Unfortunately their low thermal conductivity significantly limit heat sink heat rate from heat source. Range of phase change materials application could significantly rise if their thermal conductivity could be improved.

Recently a lot of carbon structures was improved and their production became commercial. Their low

dimensions, high thermal conductivity and melting point could be easily and successfully used in thermal conductivity of phase change materials enhancement.

Some of the carbon structures were used in phase change materials thermal conductivity enhancement within original research projects. Their results show that thermal conductivity could raise at least few times.

There are no complex research that present wide range phase change materials and carbon structures used for manufacturing new composite materials with high heat capacity and enhanced thermal conductivity. In this project particular phase change materials will be mixed with all carbon structures proposed and their solubility and tendency to aggregation will be determined. Although there are first research papers on carbon nanotubes and graphene sheets use for thermal conductivity enhancement there are almost no papers on using diamond powder and fullerenes.

High heat fluxes are very important issue in modern heat transfer problems. Passive systems for heat sinks are significant in terms of construction and operation safety because they do not need any additional external supply for operating properly. The results of the proposed research will allow to increase knowledge about phase change materials solubility with carbon structures and influence of carbon structures use in composite materials with phase change materials. These kind of new materials could be used also in practical installation, like passive houses or heat radiators for microelectronics

3 Samples preparation process and samples composition

Graphene Oxide (GO) flakes – single layer graphene with diameter 10-20 micro meters were added to a various PCM's-(phase changing material) with different thermo-physical properties. The preparation procedure was unified for all PCM materials to avoid possible errors. All samples – including the reference samples were prepared in the following way: The amount of PCM require to make a composite – 5g were placed in a glass and heated on a hot plate to their melting point. After melting

down the material GO flakes were added (not in the case of reference samples) and mechanically mixed till the mixture became homogenous. The temperature was carefully measured to avoid overheating and evaporation of PCM compounds which may be indicated in the cp measurement – appearance of characteristic gaps in comparison with the reference material. The mixing procedure was carried out for at least 5 min because crucial parameter for graphene composites is their homogeneity. Please remember that the measured samples were a small fragment cut off from the composite thus without achieving homogenous composite results of thermal properties measurements could vary. During the 5th minute - the final stage of mixing the hot plate was slowly cooled down till the composite solidified. Composites were placed in the boxes and needed fragments of them were cut off to perform the measurements.

Three materials were given under thermal diffusivity investigation. The first one was pure phase change material which was CELARENE® 1M manufactured by EUROCERAS Ltd., the company from Kędzierzyn-Koźle in Poland (properties published by the manufacturer are presented in Table 1). The other samples are the composite materials of Graphene Oxide flakes with pure CELARENE® 1M. Their characterisation is presented in Table 2. The materials are pictured in Figure 1.

Property	Value	Unit
Density (23°C)	0.92-0.94	g/cm ³
Dynamic viscosity (120°C)	260	mPas
Ignition point	Over 100	°C

Table 1 Properties of CELARENE® 1M published by manufacturer [21].

Sample	Characterisation
CELARENE	Pure CELARENE® 1M with properties as in Table 1
1 to 1	Mixture of Graphene Oxide flakes and CELARENE® 1M and in volumetric ratio 1:1
2 to 1	Mixture of Graphene Oxide flakes and CELARENE® 1M and in volumetric ratio 2:1

Table 2 Samples prepared and with measured thermal diffusivity.

4 Measurement technique

Laser Flash Analysis Method (LFA) was proposed by Parker (et al.) [22] in 1961 and until now it became very popular as effective and simple method to measure thermal diffusivity and thermal conductivity. Idea is straightforward; specimen is heated on one of its side with very short in time, high power density light impulse generated by laser or flash lamp. On the second side of the specimen, infrared detector measures time response of temperature signal. After that using theoretical methods and numerical tools diffusivity is obtained. Many improvements of the method were proposed during methods' development. One of the most significant are time, ambient temperature and heat losses corrections by Cape and Lehmann [24] introduced in 1963. In the same year Cowan introduced corrections for heat losses and for high temperatures [25]. Further significant improvements for pulse-length in the Cape Lehmann model were introduced by Blumm and Opfermann in 2002 [26]. Detailed data analysis and facts known from Heat Transfer gives ability to estimate thermal diffusivity and thermal conductivity [26, 27] based on Eq. (1):

$$(1)$$

Basic theoretical background of the method presented by Parker et al. [22] involves solution of

time dependent energy conservation equation. In general this partial differential equation is given by Eq. (2):

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} \quad (2)$$

For one dimensional heat transfer with temperature only dependent components, heat flux in axial direction of the specimen is:

$$q = -k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \quad (3)$$

Additionally during analysis small temperature differences are assumed. Hence, combining Eq. (2) and Eq. (3) we get well known form of heat diffusion equation with thermal diffusivity defined by Eq. (1):

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} \quad (4)$$

Simplest model is one dimensional rod with impulse of energy density Q deposited in small volume on one of its ends. Rod has length of L , length of heat deposition volume is g and initial condition in this area is: $T(x,0) = T_0$ and for $x > g$ it is $T(x,0) = 0$. Where ρ is density, c_p specific heat capacity and k for opaque materials. Space-time dependent solution of Eq. (4) is given by formula and can be obtained by separation of variable - standard approach to parabolic PDEs [22, 27]:

$$T(x,t) = \frac{Q}{\rho c_p} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(\frac{n\pi x}{L}) \sin(\frac{n\pi g}{L})}{n\pi} \exp(-\alpha \frac{n^2 \pi^2 t}{L^2}) \quad (5)$$

Applying initial conditions:

$$T(x,0) = T_0 \quad (6)$$

Where T_m is maximal temperature

The LFA method is based on measurement of time dependent temperature signal at end of specimen, so T_m in Eq. (6). Moreover T_m and for small variable z : $T_m \approx T_0$. Applying those properties we get crucial formula:

$$\frac{T_m - T_0}{T_m} = \frac{z}{\sqrt{\pi \alpha t}} \quad (7)$$

There is common approach to find thermal diffusivity by performing Eq. (7) summation using time (t) corresponding to temperature on back surface when it equals half of maximum temperature: $T_m - T_0 = \frac{T_m - T_0}{2}$. In such case thermal diffusivity is given by formula [22], [26]:

$$\alpha = \frac{z^2}{\pi t} \quad (8)$$

Figure 1 Samples prepared.

Figure 2 Thermal diffusivity of PCM-graphene composite materials in 35-100°C temperature range

Figure 3 Thermal diffusivity of PCM-graphene composite materials in 35-100°C temperature range

Thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity can be alternatively obtained using Eq. (1). Further improvements are necessary in modern approach to LFA. Effects of graphite coatings, radiation heat losses and others are included but the basic idea is straightforward [23-27].

5 Experimental results

In the Figure 1 there are presented experimental thermal diffusivity measurement results for three materials, like presented in Table 2. The measurements were done in the temperature range from 35°C up to 100°C. For all samples and temperatures seven measurements were done. Thermal diffusivity for all the samples is decreasing with the temperature. For two samples (pure CELARENE and sample 2 to 1) in the temperature 100°C thermal diffusivity is slightly increasing. It is a result of melting point for the sample which is slightly over 100°C and probably non uniform temperature field in whole sample.

A significant increase of thermal diffusivity may be noticed with the change of Graphene Oxide flakes content in the composite material.

As presented in Figure 2 for 35°C thermal diffusivity is increasing from 0,094 to 0,134 mm²/s for 1 to 1 composite material and 0,145 mm²/s for 2 to 1 composite material.

For 100°C 1 to 1 volumetric content of graphene oxide flakes improve thermal diffusivity from 0,073 mm²/s to 0,081 mm²/s. For the 2 to 1 composite material the value of thermal diffusivity is 0,116 mm²/s.

In the Figure 3 the relative increase of thermal diffusivity for composite materials manufactured is presented. It is noticeable that the improvement of thermal diffusivity for 1 to 1 composite material has different relation than improvement of thermal diffusivity for 2 to 1 composite material. The thermal diffusivity is increasing with Graphene Oxide flakes composition ratio in the measured materials.

Thermal diffusivity enhancement for 1 to 1 Graphene Oxides flakes composition in the composite material is constantly decreasing with the temperature.

For the material with 2 to 1 the thermal diffusivity enhancement is more stable in the investigated temperature range and it is around 150% of thermal diffusivity for pure CELARENE® 1M at the appropriate temperature level.

6 Conclusions and final remarks

The thermal diffusivity and thermal conductivity are the physical parameters which has very low values for common Phase Change Materials. Because of this fact the solidification and melting processes of this materials and use of these materials in high heat flux with high frequency applications are limited.

One of the thermal diffusivity and conductivity enhancement for such materials is creating and constructing composite materials with high conduction additives. These can be different solid materials with higher thermal conductivity than the matrix material e.g. metal powders and carbon additives.

Increased thermal diffusivity and thermal conductivity which is presented in this paper is significant and shows that this way of increasing thermal properties is worth further research. The important issue are homogenization properties and influence on enthalpy properties.

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